

LINGUOCULTURAL ANALYSIS OF THE CONCEPT "GENDER" IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Annotation. The article being talked about uncovers the issues of similar and linguocultural examination of the idea "orientation" in Uzbek and English dialects. The current review presents orientation as an idea of etymological culture and portrays it as the premise that structures orientation generalizations on the material of phraseological units of English and Uzbek dialects. The writer of the article thinks about that orientation is definitely not a semantic class, however its substance can be uncovered through the examination of language structures, which makes sense of the requirement for a phonetic investigation of the social portrayal of orientation.

Keywords: Comparative, linguocultural, gender, concept, analysis, cultural representation, masculinity, femininity, roles.

Introduction. The idea of "orientation" is broadly thought of as a socio-social, desultory and psycholinguistic peculiarity. While contemplating the orientation factor in language, a linguocultural approach is advanced, including the investigation of manliness and gentility as essential social ideas. The use of the orientation approach depends on the systemic standard - understanding orientation as a socially furthermore, socially built peculiarity. Investigation of the declaration of orientation in language includes the portrayal of orientation in language through phonetic assets and an entire arrangement of elements (from ethnic and socio-social to individual psychological). In discourse conduct, ladies are described by deviations from the principle theme and changes in jobs; men tend not to go amiss from the point and intrude on the questioner all the more regularly. In current etymology, orientation highlights are considered in blend with status, social bunch, instructive level, situational setting also, considering what is happening in the public arena. Interest in the ways of naming people of various orientation and the orientation classification as such has profound roots: the connection between the linguistic orientation also, the extralinguistic classification "orientation" is viewed as the main one. The standard thought that ladies are more enthusiastic than men prompts the way that the same types of discourse conduct in men are deciphered as unbiased and in ladies as enthusiastic. All phonetic investigations of propensity are reliant and

correlative. The current sociolinguistic model of language and discourse working incorporates a design of reliant and interrelated parts, associated, from one perspective, with physiological what's more, neuropsychological highlights of the individual and, then again, with the particularity of individual discourse code development affected by friendly (social, ethnic, and so on) and financial (having a place with a certain bunch, layer, class, and so forth) factors. The investigation of men's discourse addresses the want of men to limit their emotionality (particularly any indications of delicacy), utilizing unbiased jargon.^[1]

The investigation of the method for articulation of language units, conveying feelings in the discourse of ladies, uncovers emotionality, which is appeared at various levels. It is noticed the craving of ladies to utilize, other than nonpartisan, generally "female" jargon, wealthy in examinations, representations, ovals and facetious inquiries. When dissecting the inflection of male and female voices such peculiarities as the discourse skill of ladies, avant-gardism or traditionalism, emotionality, economic wellbeing and social discourse are recognized. The issue of discourse (intonational) skill is not set in stone by contrasting female and male readings of the text in the gathering of something similar societal position. Instructed ladies are as capable in pitch standards for perusing as men. In orientation phonetics "orientation imbalance" is of interest, in light of the fact that its review adds to the profound review, and at times update of the word-arrangement and nominative frameworks of language. In English against the foundation of certain accomplishments of women's liberation, reflected in the language (the presence of such words as cop, alpha predator, careerwoman), the male strength is saved, as just at the semantic level the classification of orientation shows up. In English the idea "man" communicates the signifying "human", and "lady" has no this importance. The English lexeme "man" means the idea "man" from an overall perspective and furthermore assumes control over the assignment of all the most desirable characteristics intrinsic in an individual. As in numerous Indo-European dialects, nonpartisan words it are manly to signify people of the two genders words. The development of ladylike words in English is produced using the expressions of the male orientation. The orientation approach depends on the thought that it isn't the natural or physical contrasts among people that matter, yet the social

¹ Gregory Titelman. (2000). Random House of America's Popular Proverbs and Sayings. Random House. P.56.

and social importance that society appends to these distinctions. The current review presents orientation as a idea of etymological culture and portrays it as the premise that structures orientation generalizations on the material of phraseological units of English and Uzbek dialects. Orientation is certifiably not an etymological class, yet its substance can be uncovered through the examination of language structures, which makes sense of the requirement for an etymological investigation of the social portrayal of orientation. L.Gordon believes orientation to be a fundamental aspect of the social construction of society. Having thought about various perspectives of language specialists, we can characterize orientation as an idea or peculiarity of mental nature, showed in the method for language and elements of individuals' discourse action regarding having a place with a specific orientation.

To choose solely orientation stamped phraseological units from the general phraseological asset of the dialects under study, we will propose the accompanying models for the choice of orientation checked English and Uzbek phraseological units: 1. Linguistic standard. In English, phraseological units with individual pronouns he (он - у), she (она - у), his (его - унинг), him (его, ему - унга), her (её - унинг, ей - унга) are gendermarked: His Majesty's workers - актёры; he is so moronic you can sell him the Brooklyn Bridge - он набитый дурак - у мутлақо аҳмоқдир. Be that as it may, in numerous English axioms with the individual pronoun he there is a peculiarity of orientation balance furthermore, such adages can be utilized in connection to ladies: he giggles best who giggles last - хорошо смеётся тот, кто смеётся последним - охирги марта кулган киши яхши кулади. This is what is appeared in androcentrism in English sentence structure. In the Uzbek language, the distinguishing proof of orientation shading of phraseological articulations with the assistance of syntactic rule is troublesome, in light of the fact that it has no pronouns, demonstrating a specific orientation. 2. The morphological standard essentially depends on the substance of - er and - or additions in the construction of English phraseological units, demonstrating the male orientation and the addition - ess, demonstrating the female orientation: stock entertainer - актёр, входящий в постоянную труппу определённого театра - маълум бир театрнинг доимий труппаси таркибига кирадиган актёр; intruding duchess - суестьющаяся дама, любящая командовать, но сама ничего не делающая - буйруқ беришни яхши кўрадиган, лекин ўзи ҳеч нарса қилмайдиган гавжум хоним.. Notwithstanding, not all English phraseological articulations containing the part with the addition - er and - or on the other hand mean the male orientation, they can additionally mean a lady: high kicker - a silly young lady who likes

diversion; support burglars - who wedded somebody a lot more youthful than herself. 3. Lexical basis of choosing gender-marked phraseological articulations in English and Uzbek not entirely set in stone by the substance of the accompanying gender-indexed parts:^[2] a) Proper names, for example manly furthermore, female names: Хўжа Аҳрорнинг моли - these things have a place with Hoja Ahrar (for example things that are not accessible to anybody); enormous John - a select. b) Nouns, orientation stamped lexemes demonstrating a specific orientation: пайғамбар ёши - the age of the Prophet Muhammad (i.e., 63 years); оппоқ қиз - sweet young lady (amiable location to a young lady); the old woman - mother, elderly person; freedom man - mariner on leave or vacation. c) Gender-recorded connection terms: оппоқ дада - granddad; if mother could see us now 4. The semantic standard of choosing orientation checked phraseological units is the most troublesome, on the grounds that English and Uzbek style teems with units that are not orientation set apart by their part structure, however on the off chance that we go to the overall significance of these parts, we can find that they mean either a man or a lady. Think about the Uzbek expressiveness боши қоронғи - pregnant (in the main time of pregnancy). On the off chance that we take apart this phraseological unit into discrete parts, we acquire the lexemes бош - head and қоронғи - dim. These singular lexemes are not orientation set apart at all, yet together they framed a phraseological unit signifying a lady in the beginning phase of pregnancy. Assuming we investigate the English diction relax reptile - a social bum, it additionally doesn't contain an orientation part: relax is a spot for rest and diversion, reptile is a creature (reptile). Together they mean a man who isn't occupied with a certain business and likes to spend time in diversion clubs and bars.

Consequently, every one of the recorded models for choosing orientation stamped phraseological units takes into account certain progressions or exemptions. Along these lines, all the rules ought to be applied together to obviously indicate the orientation selected by the semantics of a specific phraseological unit. Orientation generalizations distinguished on the material of English and Uzbek manner are separated into: 1) male generalization; 2) the generalization of a lady. The orientation generalization capacities at the degree of the language framework, with respect to the orientation idea, it is addressed a

² Gordon L. (1990). Gender and Higher Education in in the Progressive Era. New Haven, London: Yale University Press. P.258.

lot more extensive than the orientation generalization. The orientation idea can be completed at the lexical-phraseological level what's more, at the degree of whole texts. Not the all the time orientation idea harmonizes with the orientation generalization, going against the norm, in current English furthermore, Uzbek dialects there is a sure inconsistency between orientation generalizations and orientation ideas. Society creates, individuals' cliché sentiments about existing or prior models of people change, what's more, these progressions don't necessarily figure out how to be ideal recorded and reflected in language, in specific in lexicographic sources. The examination of English expressions permitted us to assemble the accompanying semantic arrangement:

1. Outer attributes: Appearance: Teddy kid - олифта бола, muscles of steel - бақуват, a cart bird (jarg.) - чиройли, олифта қиз, a model (coll.) - чиройли, гўзал қиз, a dream come true young lady (am.) - газета еки журналдан қирқиб олинган гўзал актрисанинг расми, a peroxide blonde - малла сочли қиз; Natural attributes: the girl of Eve (cf. Eve's girl) – Еванинг қизи (аёл); the more vulnerable vessel - замонавий тилда аёл маъносида ишлатилинади; Mature: a little man - ёш бола; an unlicked offspring - қўпол ўспирин; an old feline, қари, жоғи тинмайдиган кампир; a bread also, margarine miss (facetious) – мактаб ёшидаги қизча; The regenerative capacity of a lady: in the family way (conversationally) - ҳомиладор; In English phraseological jargon a man is addressed, from one viewpoint, as the solid sex: a's man (coll.) - ҳақиқий эркак; red blood - қўрқмас, ботир; play the man - ўзини эркак кишига хос тутиш; what's more, on the other hand, as a powerless animal to describe a lady like, nostalgic man: an elderly person (offensive) - ўзини номардларча тутиш; a Miss Nancy - мулойим, юмшоқ йигит.^[3]

2. Mental qualities: Moral and moral qualities: women (woman's) man - хотинбоз; a pharmacy (or then again pharmacy) rancher (am. jarg.) - ишёқмас, ялқов; gay Lothario - хотинбоз, a hot (warm) child (am. jarg.) - енгилтак, беҳаё қиз; Among the expressions addressed to a man, the qualities of incredible skill and craftsmanship stick out: Jack of all exchanges - қўли гул, мохир уста; Mr. Fixit - мохир, буюк уста. In English expressiveness, a lady's scholarly capacities are assessed contrarily: stupid Dora (jarg.)/cousin Betty (coll.) - ақлсиз, нодон қиз; Ladies are ascribed to chattiness: old spouses' stories - аёл кишининг мишмиш ва ғийбатлари; old wife - чақимчи; Female characteristics incorporate freedom: paramour of

³ Jespersen J. (1998). The woman / the feminist critique of language / ed. by D. Cameron. L., 137 p.

the circumstance/to be one's own escort – ўз тақдирига эга булиш / тақдири ва хаётини ўзи хал қилиш; a lady of honor - ҳалол ва тўғрисиўз аёл. 3. Social attributes: Marriage: Miss Right (informal) - бўлажак умр йўлдоши (аёл); Mr. Perfect - бўлажак умр йўлдоши (эркак). The axiom 'a decent spouse makes a decent spouse' - яхши эрнинг аёли ҳам яхши - stresses the right of the man as the head and his obligation regarding his accomplice; Connections between individuals: one of the young men - вафодор одам; huge kid қария, дўст; women first (informal) - эркак аёлга хурмат билан йўл берганда; Family relations: every son follows his old man's example (modifier) - олмани олдига олма тушади; Unmarried life: a stag party (informal) - бўйдоқлар компанияси; single blessedness (kidding) – бўйдоқлар хаёти; Family relationship: stepbrother - ўгай ака-укалар; sworn siblings - тутинган ака-укалар; (the) old woman - умр йўлдош. 1. Proficient exercises: a man of letters - ёзувчи; business specialist – ишлаб чиқаришда маслаҳатчи; Tom Tailor - чевар; the main woman - бош ролдаги актриса. In this gathering are recognized the phrases signifying callings connected with regulation, armed force and naval force, governmental issues, and so forth. Socioprofessional movement is determinative for men and covers the most critical circles of human action.

Conclusion. Thus, a man's professional activity is extremely important for English-speaking society, since the amount of income and the prestige of a man's work determines his social status and that of his family as a whole. Social and economic reforms of the late twentieth century also influenced the role of women in society. Stereotypical ideas about the role of women, as represented in the phrases have undergone significant changes, which are naturally associated with the correctness of language.

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